

EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION STUDY OF GFRP WITH LOCAL FIBRE DEFLECTION UNDER BEARING LOADS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper deals with experimental and simulation studies of glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) with local fibre deflection (ND) and fibre cut (NC) under double and single shear bearing loads. Unidirectional (UD) $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ and quasi-isotropic (QI) $[0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ GFRP laminate configurations were investigated. In this study, stress-strain behaviour, ultimate bearing strength, strain and failure modes were recorded. The results show that the QI have significantly greater ultimate bearing strength than UD and the ND are superior to the NC in strain energy absorption. They also point out that the ND are failing under non-catastrophic failure mode, which is relevant in later design process.

In addition to experimental work, the simulation of the mechanical behaviour for notched cut and notched deflected specimens is aimed. So, this work gives a holistic base for determination of material description and understanding of effects of local fibre deflection. The simulation model includes the failure behaviour and material degradation due to failures to precisely predict material's mechanical properties. Moreover, it is modified to the investigated bearing tests and the occurring failure modes to optimise calculation times and to simplify material description. The results show that the developed simulation model can precisely predict the maximum bearable loads, the beginning of material degradation after first failure and damage progression for small displacements after first failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the Europe 2020 Strategy, high standards for future mobility sector are set and lightweight material will be getting more and more important in future. Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) already make an important contribution today in modern lightweight materials and their importance will grow continuously. Rivet and bolt joints are industrial joining standards for several FRP applications and for highly loaded structures, especially in aircraft industry, by which the FRP are drilled during post processing [1]. The post processing can lead to severe damage and primary failures; net-tension and shear-out, due to high notch coefficients by damaged fibres in such applications. This results in a strongly decrease of maximum transferrable loads at joints [2-4]. Therefore, in this work, on an improvement of common FRP through local fibre deflection at the hole area is focused. An objective is to assess the effects of local fibre deflection at joint area and ply orientation on failure strength and on failure mode. Ten samples each case of NC and ND fibre structure, were tested according to ASTM D5961/D5961M-17 [5]. An experimental characterisation of mentioned structures under single and double shear bearing loads was conducted. Moreover, a material model for the investigated structures was developed and a FEM-simulation of double shear bearing tests was performed. The results of experiments of epoxy based GFRP under double shear bearing load were compared to the simulation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Sample Production and Measurements

Unidirectional glass textile HP-U400E from HP-Textiles with an area weight of 417 g/m² is used. The used epoxy resin system is composed of RIMR135 and the related amine-based curing agent RIMH1366 from Hexion. There are two investigated laminate configurations which are unidirectional (UD) [0°/0°/0°/0°]_s and quasi-isotropic (QI) [0°/+45°/-45°/90°]_s, all of which consist out of eight layers. In each laminate configuration, notched deflected (ND) and notched cut (NC) fibre structure were considered. A sketch of the laminate configuration and fibre structure is shown in Figure 1. In this paper, the specimen notation is defined as shown in Table 1.

The manufacturing process used for all specimens was a combined vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) and a heating press. The laminate was firstly impregnated by VARI at room temperature and then compacted under a heating press at 80°C for one hour. For a constant laminate thickness, it procured with a defined distance between upper and lower mould. For fully curing, tempering in an oven at 80°C for four hours after the compaction was applied.

All test specimens were cut with a diamond-coated cutting blade into desired dimension, shown in Figure 2, according to ASTM D5761 [5]. For prevention of external damages from drilling tool at holes, they were then drilled with a special solid drilling tool for fibre composites to produce a hole diameter of $\text{Ø}6_{-0.000}^{+0.012}$ mm to fit with the used fastener with the dimension of $\text{Ø}6_{-0.01}^{-0.04}$ mm. The structure of fibre deflection was manufactured manually during textile stacking step with the help of a hole holder. Double shear and single shear bearing behaviour was studied here. All test procedures are regarded to the ASTM D5761 [5] and were conducted with a universal testing machine Z-100KN from ZwickRoell with a testing speed of 1 mm/min.

For double shear bearing tests, ten specimens of each variation were tested up to failure to determine the average bearing stress, strength, strain and their failure mode.

For single shear bearing tests, ten specimens of each variation were tested up to a displacement of the half of the nominal hole diameter, which is 3 mm. Constantly, the average bearing stress, strength, strain and occurred failure mode were recorded.

During tests, the specimens were equipped with an axial extensometer to determine local displacement of specimens with a gauge length of 50 mm. The hole of specimen was placed in the middle of the extensometer with a fastener. The average thickness of specimens is 2.45 ± 0.05 mm. In addition, the fibre volume fraction reaches 55% in average [6-7].

The bearing stress (σ_B), ultimate bearing strength ($\sigma_{B,ul}$), bearing strain (ε_B), ultimate bearing strain ($\varepsilon_{B,ul}$), average ultimate bearing strength ($\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$) and stiffness (E) are defined as followed:

$$\sigma_B = F / (d \cdot h) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{B,ul} = F_{max} / (d \cdot h) \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_B = (l - l_0) \cdot 100 / l_0 \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{B,ul} = (l_{max} - l_0) \cdot 100 / l_0 \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{B,ul,avg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{B,ul,i}}{n} \quad (5)$$

$$E = \frac{\sigma_B}{\varepsilon_B} \quad (6)$$

where:

- σ_B = bearing stress in MPa,
- F = force at a certain data point in N,
- d = hole diameter in mm,
- h = thickness of specimen in mm,

$\sigma_{B,ul}$ = ultimate bearing strength in MPa,
 F_{max} = maximum force prior to failure in N,
 ϵ_B = bearing strain in %,
 l = displacement of extensometer at a certain data point in mm,
 l_0 = gauge length of extensometers at the start point (50 mm),
 $\epsilon_{B,ul}$ = ultimate bearing strain in %,
 l_{max} = displacement of extensometer at the maximum force prior to failure in mm,
 $\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$ = Average ultimate bearing strength of n specimens in MPa,
 $\sigma_{B,ul,i}$ = Average ultimate bearing strength of specimen i in MPa,
 n = Numbers of all specimens and
 E = Stiffness or Young's modulus of specimen in MPa per %.

Figure 1: Laminate configuration and fibre structure; (a) unidirectional (UD)-notched-deflected (ND), (b) unidirectional (UD)-notched-cut (NC), (c) quasi-isotropic (QI)-notched-deflected (ND) and (d) quasi-isotropic (QI)-notched-cut (NC)

Specimen notation	X	-	XX	-	XX
Type of bearing test:	_____				
D = double shear, S = single shear					
Laminate configuration:	_____				
UD = unidirectional, QI= quasi-isotropy					
Fibre structure:	_____				
ND = notched deflected, NC = notched cut					

Table 1: Specimen notation

Figure 2: Specimen geometries (all dimensions in mm)

Due to a consistent comparison of results, all results of mechanical tests were normalised by the individual measured fibre volume fraction of certain specimen regarding to [6, 7].

2.2 Results and Discussion

2.2.1 Stress-strain curves and ultimate bearing strength

The average stress-strain curves of double shear bearing and single shear bearing test are illustrated in Figure 3 (a) and (b) respectively. Regarding to the stress-strain curves, it is obvious that GFRP with quasi-isotropic laminate configuration are offering higher strength than unidirectional GFRP in both fibre structures (ND/NC). In both laminate configurations (UD/QI), comparing the fibre structures, the notched cut fibre structure (NC) have significantly greater stiffness than the notched deflected fibre structure (ND). The ND structure of fibres around the hole area is aimed to reduce a sharp stress concentration resulting from cut fibre path from conventional drilling process by bypassing the acting force with deflected fibre path. However, this tends to increase unequal distribution of local fibre volume fraction and resin accumulation around the hole that results in lower stiffness of the structure under testing. Nevertheless, the deflected fibre structure (ND) exhibits significantly greater ultimate stress and ultimate strain, which results in greater absorption of strain energy.

Figure 3: Stress-strain comparison of notched deflected and notched cut fibre structure in UD and QI laminate configuration; (a) under double shear bearing test, (b) under single shear bearing test

The trends of stress-strain curves of specimens under double shear and single shear bearing test are consistent to each other. Under single shear bearing load, the specimens demonstrate greater strain by equal stress in comparison to double shear bearing load. This can be attributed to different loads applied at the hole area; full fastener area, fully axial load in double shear bearing and partial fastener area, partial bending and partial axial load in single shear test.

Data of average ultimate bearing strength, ultimate bearing strain, stiffness and strength ratio is shown in Table 2, presenting good reproducibility of each testing variation and acceptable maximum of coefficient of variance of 13.3% in the case of S-UD-NC. The distribution of variance is caused by possible errors from manufacturing, experiment and calculation. Table 2 also presents data of strength ratio (σ_{ND}/σ_{NC}) of each double, single shear test, UD and QI laminate configuration. The strength ratio is defined by the ultimate bearing strength of deflected fibre structure divided by the ultimate bearing strength of cut fibre structure. Considering strength ratio of unidirectional laminate lay-up (UD) that illustrates a slightly greater strength ratio in both double and single shear bearing tests of 1.08. Conversely, the strength ratio of ND, quasi-isotropic laminate configuration (QI) is inferior to notched cut fibre structure (NC) of 0.94 and 0.71 in double and single shear bearing test respectively. However, it is to be noticed that the data of single shear bearing test is not from the actual ultimate bearing strength of the structure because the test was stopped at the displacement of 3 mm or 6% of strain for initial failure observation. Its ultimate bearing strength can be greater than the data of this current study and the impairment of the strength ratio in single shear bearing test could be less.

Type of testing		Double shear bearing				Single shear bearing			
		D-UD-ND	D-UD-NC	D-QI-ND	D-QI-NC	S-UD-ND	S-UD-NC	S-QI-ND	S-QI-NC
$\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$	(MPa)	179.82	166.07	483.09	511.40	161.42	149.38	339.95	476.57
S.D.	(MPa)	12.85	7.17	19.79	19.22	17.12	19.85	26.95	25.92
(C.V.)	(%)	(7.1)	(4.3)	(4.1)	(3.8)	(10.6)	(13.3)	(7.9)	(5.4)
$\varepsilon_{B,ul}$ at $\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$	(%)	1.97	0.85	5.07	1.92	3.99	1.39	6	6
E	(GPa)	10.08	47.04	22.02	34.79	4.39	33.37	7.19	21.07
σ_{ND}/σ_{NC}	(-)	1.08	-	0.94	-	1.08	-	0.71	-

Table 2: Data of average ultimate bearing strength, strain and strength ratio

2.2.2 Failure mode after double shear bearing test

Figure 4 presents observed failure modes occurred after double shear bearing test. The first failures (e.g. initial matrix and interface crack) occur before the specimens reach their maximum strength. In UD specimens (Figure 4 (a) and (b)), the failure begins with the matrix cracking and fibre-matrix interface cracking at the vicinity of the hole. The first cracks then progress along the direction and reverse the direction of bearing load, which develops to further fibre-matrix interface cracking and to shear out damage (in NC case). Due to the shear out damage, which is one of primary failures, damages in D-UD-ND are less critical than in D-UD-NC.

Figure 4 (c) and (d) show damages of D-QI-ND and D-QI-NC specimens respectively. Both specimen types show same failure behaviour in bearing because the load is transferred to a greater area as a result of quasi-isotropic configuration. According to [8], the bearing failure mode is non-catastrophic and desirable in design stage for fibre composites. In addition, in contrast to UD specimens, damages in QI specimens only develop towards the direction of the bearing force (none in reverse to the load direction). In D-QI-NC specimens, we can also observe delamination of laminate layer, what can be observed after testing. D-QI-ND in contrast achieves less laminate layer delamination.

Figure 4: Failure mode after double shear bearing test of GFRP specimens; D-UD-ND (a), D-UD-NC (b), D-QI-ND (c) and D-QI-NC (d)

3 SIMULATION

For further steps a simulation model with integrated damage behaviour shall be developed for the double shear tests. A model like this allows to precisely predict the maximum bearable loads of the structure and calculations of the failure behaviour with ply-wise analysis of damage initiation and propagation. In the next steps the determination of all necessary parameters will be shown and a comparison to experimental data will be given as a proof of the model's quality. Previous studies [9] have already shown clearly that simulative approaches for describing the mechanical behaviour of local fibre deflections offer promising results, near to real behaviour.

The software ANSYS version 19.1 with the module ACP Pre-Processor is used. As damage initiation criteria, the criteria according to Hashin are applied, which are using more than one stress component for evaluation of the failure modes. These failure modes are tensile and compressive failure of the fibres and the matrix. Developed for two-dimensional laminates, these criteria should give good approximation for the investigated structures.

Different damage behaviour has been developed for calculating the stiffness reduction of materials after failure initiation for simulating overloaded parts. For simulating the damage behaviour and the reduction of material properties, two different types can be identified, progressive damage evolution and continuum damage mechanics. In the first procedure, the material's stiffness is instantly reduced based on the damage variables. In the second procedure, the continuum damage mechanics, the damage variables will be gradually increased, based on the energy amount dissipated for the damage modes. A progressive damage evolution law with an instant stiffness reduction is used here for two reasons. First, because a brittle anisotropic material is investigated here, a progressive damage behaviour will offer sufficient precision for prediction of the post damage behaviour. Second, it leads to shorter calculation times compared to continuous damage mechanics and will improve the performance of the calculation.

The simulations in this study will be done in three steps. First, the major failure behaviour will be investigated by theoretical thoughts and some basic simulations to identify the most important damage variables. In a second step, a parameter study will be used to optimise the damage variables, identified in the first step. In the third and last step, simulation models for the previous samples, which were investigated by experimental work, will be created to proof if FEM-simulations can be used to predict the mechanical behaviour of the investigated samples for bearing load.

The models for the finite element simulations with the boundary conditions can be found in Figure 5 and Figure 6. The simulations will be processed by a half model to reduce the calculation times. The cutting surface is supported by frictionless bearing and the drilling is mounted by a compression-only support. A fixed displacement is applied to the front surface and the reaction force in the drilling area is calculated.

Figure 5: FE model with meshing and boundary conditions for notched cut specimens

Figure 6: FE model with meshing and boundary conditions for notched deflected specimens

3.1 Identification of major failures

For bolted joints and rivet joints, the load will be transferred by compression load in the contact zone. The distribution and strength can be described with formulas for Hertzian pressure contact problems. So, a first critical zone in the laminate can be identified in the upper part of the drilling in the contact zone between the laminate and the bolt (Figure 5-A). A second potential critical area can be found besides the drilling (Figure 5-B). The compression load in the upper part of the drilling will be transferred via the fibres to the clamping area and a stress concentration besides the drilling will occur. Depending on the load cases and the geometry of the samples, different damage behaviour will dominate and here a failure of the structure because of bearing stress or net tension is generally possible. For reducing the calculation times, the model will be simplified, and damage variables only will be optimised for the necessary damage cases. Therefore, these two zones will be investigated by a basic simulation to establish the major failure case for the investigated double shear bearing test.

The basic simulations without damage behaviour show that the parts are failing because of matrix overloading and no damage of fibres, according to Hashin failure criterion, occurs. Therefore, in the model a reduction for matrix tensile and matrix compression failure will be applied and optimised in a parameter study.

3.2 Parameter Study

Because the basic simulation in previous part has shown that only a damage of the matrix occurs, the damage variables for the fibres will be set to zero to simplify the model. The damage reduction factor for matrix compression d_{mc} and for matrix tension d_{mt} was varied between 0.2 and 0.9 in steps of 0.1 to cover a large range of possible values and combinations. All data will be compared to the mean values from experiments for the notched cut specimens of double shear tests. As a reference to the simulations with damage behaviour, results without damage progression $d_{mt} = 0$; $d_{mc} = 0$, is calculated as well. A selection of different simulation results is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Optimisation of damage variables between 0.2 and 0.9

As shown, small values for the damage variables are leading to inaccurate description of the mechanical behaviour for the investigated specimens. The illustrated combinations of $d_{mt} = 0.8$ and $d_{mc} = 0.9$ respectively $d_{mt} = 0.9$ and $d_{mc} = 0.9$ are showing a good correlation between experimental mean values and simulated mechanical behaviour. Results for displacements higher than 0.15 mm (black arrow) are described better by factors of $d_{mt} = 0.9$ and $d_{mc} = 0.9$. Therefore, in the next steps a more precise determination of best combination of damage variables is done. Both will be set to 0.92, 0.95 and 0.97 and all possible combinations between them will be simulated. Selected results are given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Optimisation of damage variables between 0.92 and 0.97

The results for investigated combinations have shown similar mechanical behaviour and an overall good conformity between simulation results and experimental mean values. The maximum force for experimental mean values is reached by a deformation of 0.34 mm and is fitting to simulation data. The maximum yieldable force, when the first ply failure occurs, is calculated by 2450 N and in experiment failure begins at about 2300 N. The progress, after the first failure, can be modelled in a proper way and the strain, where fast failure growth occurs, can be shown. The best fit is given by a combination of $d_{mt} = 0.92$ and $d_{mc} = 0.92$, especially for displacements larger than 0.25 mm (black arrow). Therefore, the damage variables will be set to these values for all further simulations.

3.3 Comparison to Experiments

With the information from previous steps, simulation models for all investigated double shear tests will be created. The meshing and all boundary conditions were processed in the same way like in the previous simulations. Also, the damage variables will be set like before, which means, that no stiffness reduction for damage of fibres will be used and a stiffness reduction for matrix damages were set to 0.92. A maximum strain of 3 % is set for the models. The simulation results of all four specimen types were shown in Figure 9 to Figure 12. Again, the results from the simulations were compared to the mean values of the relating experimental tests. Additionally, the displacements were coloured where, according to the simulations, the first ply-failure occurs.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 are showing the results for notched cut specimens, Figure 11 and Figure 12 respectively for notched deflected specimens.

In general, the simulations are showing a good accuracy compared to the mean values of experimental data. Especially for small displacements a proper description of the material's behaviour is given by the simulations with used damage variables.

Also, the beginning of material degradation (marked circle in grey) caused by first cracks can be predicted with a high accuracy. Moreover, the results have shown that the progressive material degradation after first failure for notched cut and notched deflected specimens can be described by the used model. The general strain-stress-progression as well as the maximum stress limits can be predicted by the used simulation models.

Generally, the results for quasi-isotropic specimen seem to be slightly more accurate than unidirectional specimens. A possible cause of this could be the structure of the laminate and the orientation of the individual layers. In the case of loads transverse to the fibre or at an angle of 45°, the load within the matrix increases and the influence of the fibres decreases, so that more precisely the used model can reproduce this. With increasing strains, the accuracy of the model is decreasing and differences between predicted progression and experimental data increases. Because the models which were used here are optimised for short calculation times and simple mechanical behaviour of the materials, damage variables for fibres were not included.

Figure 9: Simulation results for unidirectional notched cut specimens under double shear bearing load

Figure 10: Simulation results for quasi-isotropic notched cut specimens under double shear bearing load

Figure 11: Simulation results for unidirectional notched deflected specimens under double shear bearing load

Figure 12: Simulation results for quasi-isotropic notched deflected specimens under double shear bearing load

But, with increasing strains and ongoing failures of matrix, the stresses inside the fibres increase due to load redistribution and damage of fibres potentially will appear, caused by overloading them. This effect can be neglected for small loads, but with increasing loads further deviations and an increase in inaccuracies occur. The developed models cannot consider this, which leads to a limitation of valid stress-strain-values and progression for large strains cannot be calculated exactly.

At this point, however, the results of D-QI-ND should be pointed out, which shows a high correspondence between simulation and experimental results in the whole investigated area. Since quasi-isotropic structures in particular are used in the technical field, the investigated fibre deflection is a promising approach for increasing the performance of an overall structure.

Both the experimental investigations and the simulative approach show a significantly improved load-bearing behaviour of the structure. Paired with the designed material model and the optimized damage parameters, this results in an approach for the development of a complete design tool for complex structures with integrated fibre deflections.

4 CONCLUSION

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this study:

- The present work deals with the influence of fibre deflections on bearing loads in fibre reinforced plastics. Experimental investigations as well as simulations are carried out.
- Regarding the stress-strain diagrams from experiments, significantly higher strengths for quasi-isotropic structures compared to unidirectional specimens are shown. This is in line with previous findings of classical bolt connections.
- Comparing the fibre structures ND and NC, the ND have slightly greater average ultimate double and single shear bearing strength ($\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$) in case of UD than in case of QI of 8%. In contrast, in QI layer configuration, the NC structure is characterised with a slightly superior in $\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$ than the ND of 6% under double shear bearing load. The difference is significant in case of single shear bearing load as the $\sigma_{B,ul,avg}$ of NC is 29% greater than the ND.
- Considering strain behaviour, in both UD and QI, the ND is characterised by significantly greater strain energy absorption in comparison to the conventional NC structure.
- Considering failure modes of double shear bearing load, all ND (both UD and QI) and NC (in QI case) achieve non-catastrophic failure, e.g. bearing and fibre-matrix interface cracking. In contrast, the NC (in UD case) exhibits catastrophic failure (shear-out). Hence, the ND despite of lower stiffness provides higher flexibility in part design stage.
- The developed simulation models offer an easy method for calculating the maximum bearable loads and the material degradation in a limited range due to using a progressive material degradation model. For the notched cut (NC) and notched deflected (ND) specimens, models were presented and compared to the experimental data. High conformity between simulation and experiment can be shown.
- For the investigated double shear bearing tests, the main failures are matrix dominated, but with increasing displacements the stress concentration inside the fibres is increasing. Therefore, ignoring the damage variables for fibre failures will accelerate calculation times, but model's accuracy will decrease for high displacements. Nevertheless, the developed simulation models offer a simple method to predict the mechanical behaviour of the investigated notched cut and notched deflected specimens. The maximum bearable load and the beginning of material degradation after first failure can be predicted precisely.

All things considered, this work proves the effectiveness of the investigated fibre structures and shows the mechanisms of fibre deflections in fibre reinforced plastics for bearing loads in a holistic approach. The structures with local fibre deflection are a promising approach for improved load introduction and starting point for future research.

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